

METHODOLOGY OF FORMATION OF READING SKILLS IN PRIMARY GRADES

Kudyarova Artikgul

Student of the Faculty of primary education of
The Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12781333>

Abstract. This thesis discusses the methods of development of students' reading skills in primary reading classes, the components of the reading lesson, and the interdependence of these parts. The content and essence of the works carried out in expressive reading are explained.

Keywords: primary grade, conscious reading, correct reading, reading speed, expressive reading.

INTRODUCTION

Most of the important tasks in the education of primary school students are performed in reading classes. The purpose of elementary reading lessons, especially first grade reading lessons, is to develop students' ability to read consciously, correctly, fluently, quickly and expressively. Reading lessons play a very important role in solid learning of the knowledge given on topics related to mathematics, the world around us, etiquette and other subjects, because a child can understand the content of the text well only if he reads correctly and fluently. There are four main components of a reading lesson that are closely related to each other. They are: conscious reading, expressive reading, accurate reading and speed reading. Among these parts, conscious reading is in the leading place. In the process of conscious reading, students should be able to achieve the following: be able to tell the original and figurative meanings of the words they read, the meaning of each sentence, be able to briefly describe the content of the section, be able to understand the meaning of the text they should be able to explain the content of the text, express their attitude towards what they read. In order to develop expressive reading skills in the student, it is necessary to teach him to read effectively in an average voice, observing the meaning of what he reads, paying attention to the stops, and so on.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

In order to develop the correct reading skills, it is necessary to read without haste, without changing the position of letters, and to fully observe the rules of orthography. In order to increase the speed of reading, the conscious reading of students is of great importance. Mindful reading is reading the text with complete and clear understanding. Activities related to conscious reading teach students to deeply understand the content of the text being read, to think logically, and to expand their thoughts and skills. In order to improve the skill of conscious reading, questions and tasks are given at the end of the textbooks.

RESULTS

Students are gradually taught to be able to divide the text into parts, put a suitable title on it, draw pictures that reveal the content of each part, and find questions. First, work is carried out with texts that are small in size and simple in content, and then with texts that are large in size and more complex in content. One of the tools that helps to make reading more conscious is to read correctly. When reading, without making mistakes, without breaking

words, without omitting or replacing sounds and syllables, correctly pronounce the last syllables, i.e. suffixes, following the rules of orthography. Formation of correct reading skills is carried out in the whole process of reading. Correct and fast reading skills are formed only if reading is conscious. In the process of reading, it is especially important to teach children to monitor themselves, to develop a desire to read without mistakes, quickly and correctly, especially in the first grade reading classes. Reading speed depends on conscious, fluent reading. Increasing reading speed is achieved by reading syllable by syllable outside the text of multisyllabic and difficult-to-spell words. Increase reading speed by practicing reading words and sentences written in printed and written letters aloud, reading in chorus, reading internally, reading texts in roles.

The more the child reads, the faster the reading speed will increase. The knowledge given in the reading lesson is deepened by making the child read more books outside of the classroom. In order to increase the reading speed of students, it is appropriate if the following activities are carried out during the lesson [1].

Before the start of the lesson, the teacher writes some sentences and words from today's text on the board in printed letters and temporarily closes it. Students open their books and look at today's text and the word written on the board or they try to find the word quickly from the text. Cards with questions or tasks written on them are distributed to the desks. With the permission of the teacher, children read the questions and tasks written on the cards and look for answers to these questions and tasks in the text. Conducting a "quick reading competition" gives special pleasure to children. It is said that every child should start reading the text at the same time and finish reading the text by a certain time. The children who read first are marked and sit down to prepare to retell what they have read. The winners of the competition will be awarded with a star. Expressive reading means to pronounce the words correctly, to understand the content of the work, to understand the feelings expressed in the work, the inner experiences of the characters, and the mental mood. Children are impressionable. The teacher narrates the work with emotion, achieves a deep impact on the children, and in some cases manages to keep it well in their memory, the content of the work and the work of the participants in it seem like a rule of life for them. In order for the content of the work to be fully understood by the students, the teacher himself must carefully prepare to read it expressively and tell a story. Expressive reading is an indicator of conscious reading, because a student who is able to understand the meaning of the text will also acquire expressive reading skills. Mindful reading helps to develop and strengthen expressive reading skills. As conscious, accurate, and fluent reading skills are developed, effective reading skills also grow.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Work on the work in reading classes should be organized in such a way that the analysis of the content of the work is aimed at improving reading skills. Correct reading is reading without mistakes, without mistakes, and the sound of the word is without breaking the composition of letters and grammatical forms, without omitting the sound or syllable in the word, without adding another sound, without changing the position of the letters, pronouncing it clearly, putting the accent on the word correctly is reading. M. Odilova and T. Ashrapova state that "All the requirements set to the standards of literary pronunciation also apply to the ability to read correctly." Correct reading is again defined as follows: "Correct reading is a sound copy of the material without errors and smoothly." Therefore, correct

reading is reading based on literary and orthoepic standards without violating the sound structure and grammatical form of the word.

Correct reading depends on the length and brevity of the word, the reader's vocabulary, i.e. how much he knows the lexical meaning of the word, and the syllabic and morphemic composition of the word. Students often make mistakes for the following reasons [7]:

1. Since there is no thorough synthesis between pronouncing a word and understanding its meaning, the child sees the sound side of the word first and is in a hurry to pronounce it. He ignores the meaning of the word.
2. If the word has many syllables, the child will make a mistake if he has not heard it before.
3. Makes a mistake due to not knowing the meaning of the word.
4. Makes the mistake of reading quickly.
5. Correct reading depends on the light and the fall of the light.
6. They have difficulty reading words with closed syllables in the middle and at the end of the consonant sound.

Preparation for expressive reading is conditionally divided into three stages:

1. To understand the exact content of the work, to analyze the behavior of the persons participating in it, to determine the idea of the work, that is, to understand the ideological and thematic basis of the work, its images as a whole with artistic means.
2. Determining where to stop (pause) in the text, the place of the logical emphasis, and the pace of reading.
3. To practice reading, read the text again to be able to voice the author's opinion, his attitude to the described events and participants.

CONCLUSIONS

Analysis of the content and ideological direction of the work is carried out in connection with teaching expressive reading. In teaching expressive reading, the main task is to understand the content of the text, to express one's attitude to the events narrated by the author. The expressive reading of the work by the teacher is important for the formation of expressive reading skills in students.

References:

1. Muhabbat Umarova –Third grade reading lessons|| Tashkent 2014. –World of creativity|| publishing house.
2. ЕРМАТОВА, Р. О. (2018). УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ВРЕМЕННЫМ УЧЕНИЕМ ДЛЯ СТУДЕНТОВ С ОБУЧЕНИЕМ ИНВАЛИДЫ. Наука среди нас, (7), 85-88.
3. Ermatova, R. O. (2018). ADVANTAGES OF THE TECHNIQUE" WHAT/HOW/WHY OUTLINES" IN DEVELOPING PRODUCTIVE SKILLS OF THE MEDICAL STUDENTS. Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук, (6), 69-71.
4. Utegenova, S., & Rozumova, D. (2024). DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING TAX AUDIT. Modern Science and Research, 3(6).
5. Utegenova, S., & Mirzabaeva, U. (2024). TODAY'S IMPORTANCE AND PROSPECTS OF AUDIT ACTIVITIES IN UZBEKISTAN. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 4(6), 93-95.

- 6.Utegenova, S., & Oralbaeva, F. (2024). O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotiga xorijiy investitsiyalar oqimini oshirishda mamlakatning investitsion muhiti jozibadorligini oshirish. Журнал академических исследований нового Узбекистана, 1(6), 131-134.
- 7.Khasanova, S., Akisheva, N., & Zholayeva, M. (2023). Methodological aspects of tax planning in the context of sustainable development. Revista Gestão & Tecnologia, 23(3), 286-298.
- 8.Маматқулов, Б. М., & Нематов, А. А. (2021). Ўзбекистон Республикаси аҳолиси орасида COVID-19 тарқалишининг хусусиятлари.
- 9.Abdullayeva, N. (2023). AHMAD YASSAWI SECT: THE ISSUE OF ZIKR AND THE STATUS OF ZAKIR. Modern Science and Research, 2(5), 438-440.
- 10.Bazarov, S. (2024). JURNALIST VA BLOGERLAR NUTQI ETIKASI. Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика, 3(1), 36-39.
- 11.Norqulovich, S. H. (2023, October). NURILLO CHORINING BADIY ASARLARIDA MILLIY KOLORITGA XOS KO 'RINISHLAR NUTQIY JIHATDAN IFODALANISHI. In International conference on multidisciplinary science (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 25-29).
- 12.Ziyodullayeva, M., & Muxtorova, M. (2024). ABDULLA QODIRIY HAYOTI VA IJODIGA AYRIM CHIZGILAR. NRJ, 1(3), 860-863.
- 13.Muxtorova, M. (2024). MAXTUMQULI SHE'RIYATIDA AYTISHUV: AN'ANA VA IZDOSHLIK. NRJ, 1(3), 254-257.
- 14.Tajenova, G., Turdiyeva, G., Qurbanov, A., & Isakov, I. (2020). Current state and development of agricultural products exports of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Архив научных исследований, (14).
- 15.Janabay, I., Gulbahar, T., Gulayda, T., Alisher, Q., & Ilkhambek, I. (2020). Current state and development of agricultural products exports of the republic of uzbekistan. International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation, 24(8), 1684-1693.
- 16.Turdieva, G., Abishov, M., & Muratbaev, I. (2024). THE IMPACT OF CREDIT RISKS ON AN EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION IN THE FINANCIAL SERVICES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS. NRJ, 1(4), 215-225.
- 17.Beglenov, N., & Muratbaev, I. (2023). HOTEL SERVICES AS AN OBJECT OF STRATEGIC MARKETING ORIENTED TO THE CONSUMER. Science and Education in Karakalpakstan, 32(2), 175-177.
- 18.Xalmuratovich, B. S. (2024). JAHON AMALIYOTIDA AGROKLASTER TIZIMINI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISH VA YURITISH BO 'YICHA TO 'PLANGAN TAJRIBALAR TAHLILI. Scientific Journal of Actuarial Finance and Accounting, 4(04), 140-150.
- 19.Bayjanov, S. X., & Abishov, M. S. (2024). DEVELOPING THE ACTIVITY OF JOINT STOCK COMPANIES BY IMPROVING DIVIDEND POLICY. Science and innovation in the education system, 3(3), 94-97.
- 20.Sultanov, B., Nurimbetov, T., Bayjanov, S., Seyilbekov, B., & Durmanov, A. (2023, October). Trends in change and the current state of the effectiveness of land reclamation measures in agriculture. In AIP Conference Proceedings (Vol. 2921, No. 1). AIP Publishing.